

PARENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF GIRLS' EDUCATIONAL RIGHTS FROM A CITIZENSHIP PERSPECTIVE IN BARANANGSIANG VILLAGE, PERCEPTIONS OF GIRLS'S EDUCATIONAL RIGHTS CIPONGKOR DISTRICT, WEST BANDUNG REGENCY

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Abstract

Education is essential and fundamental for life. Accessing quality education without discrimination and exclusion is a human right, as education enables individuals to improve their quality of life by developing their thinking, attitudes, and behaviors. Conversely, poor quality education is a major cause of the human resource crisis. However, most communities, especially in rural areas, still do not receive education in line with national mandates. This situation is evident in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency. The traditional belief that no matter how high a woman's education, she will eventually return to the kitchen is still prevalent in this community. This study examines parents' perceptions of girls' rights to education, human rights perspectives on women's educational rights, the impact of parental perceptions on girls' educational rights, and the importance of educational equality for women in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency from a citizenship education perspective. This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data collection techniques include observation, documentation study, literature study, and interviews. Data analysis techniques involve: 1) Data collection, 2) Data reduction and categorization, 3) Data display and conclusion drawing. The results show that there must be support from the family, especially parents, both moral and material, so that girls can continue their education to higher levels, similar to boys in the village. The perspective of citizenship education on girls' educational rights is equally important as boys' educational rights, as the responsibility for the nation's progress rests on the shoulders of every citizen, both male and female.

Keywords: Parents' Perceptions of Girls' Rights, Education.

INTRODUCTION

Human Rights are a set of rights inherent in the nature of human existence as creatures of God and are His blessings that must be respected, upheld, and protected by the state, government law, for the honor and protection of human dignity without discrimination, whether male or female.

As stated by Handoyo (2015: 37), equality between men and women is very important, especially regarding multiculturalism, where society consists of men and women who cannot be separated but rather support and complement each other. Both are within a gender perspective that has equal rights to education and development in their lives.

Talking about Human Rights, this aligns with Article 26 paragraph (3) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which explains that everyone has the right to their rights, especially in education. Everyone should receive a proper education without differences, whether male or female. As stated by Nasikah in Rasid (2022: 12), education is very important, one of which is as a provision for the future.

This aligns with what Krisnalita (2018: 76) said about the importance of education: education is the most important and fundamental basis for life. With education, one can improve their quality of life, such as economic quality, quality of thought, and behavior. Conversely, poor quality education is one of the main causes of the human resource crisis. For example, when looking for work to support their lives, people must be financially independent. This will be very difficult to achieve without proper education.

However, continuing education requires support and motivation from the family, especially the parents. Parents play a very important role in a child's life, especially in continuing education. Without parental support, it is unlikely that children will have the opportunity to continue their education, especially to higher education levels. As stated by Probosiwi (2015: 51), the gap between men and women is influenced by several factors, one of which is socio-cultural factors. An example of this factor is the perception of some parents towards girls' education, where some people still think that girls do not need higher education because they will eventually return to the kitchen. This becomes one of the obstacles to the progress of Indonesian women, especially in rural areas.

Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, is one of the villages with a relatively high dropout rate for girls. The results of research in Baranangsiang Village show that many dropouts prefer to work and marry rather than continue their education, especially at the higher education level. This is due to several factors such as economic constraints, lack of parental support, and lack of interest in continuing education.

Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, is one of the villages with a relatively high dropout rate for girls. The results of research in Baranangsiang Village show that many dropouts prefer to work and marry rather than continue their education, especially at the higher education level. This is due to several factors such as economic constraints, lack of parental support, and lack of interest in continuing education.

The number of male and female residents based on age groups from 13 to 24 years, obtained from the profile of Cipongkor District in 2021, is 1,845 children. Meanwhile, the number of males and females who received education from Junior High School (SMP) to higher education levels is 521 people, with 249 males and 272 females. At the Junior High School (SMP)/Madrasah Tsanawiah (MTs) level, there are 404 students, at the Vocational High School (SMK) level there are 87 students, and those who continued to higher education in the last three years are 30 people, while early marriages reach 11 people.

Various cases currently affecting women, such as domestic violence and social exclusion, are based on low education levels. Therefore, education for women is very important and should not be overlooked. Especially differentiating between women and men, as intelligent children

are essentially born from mothers who also have intelligence. According to Widyaningsih, the lack of parental knowledge about the function of education, both formal and non-formal, results in low educational levels, especially for girls (Tismini & Susilawati, 2022: 80).

Based on the above explanation, the author is interested in exploring more deeply the perceptions of parents, of girls' rights to education, human rights perspectives on women's educational rights, the impact of parental perceptions on girls' right to education, and the importance of educational equality for women in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, from the perspective of Citizenship Education.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research is a process of discovering something that is investigated to obtain the truth and prove a phenomenon (Waruwu, 2023: 2896). This study uses a qualitative research approach. The qualitative research approach focuses on an in-depth understanding of social, cultural, or human behavioral phenomena through the interpretation of non-numerical data. According to Siyoto & Sandu (2015: 20), qualitative research emphasizes a deep understanding of a problem rather than generalizing the findings. According to Waruwu (2023: 2898), qualitative research is descriptive and analytical. Descriptive research describes events, phenomena, and situations being studied, while analytical research means interpreting and comparing the research data.

The method used in this research is the case study method. This method involves an in-depth investigation of a single case or multiple cases that are deliberately selected. Case studies allow researchers to understand phenomena in a real context, often focusing on the details and complexities of the case. In this study, the focus is on parents' perceptions of girls' right to education in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency. The case study method enables the researcher to deeply understand the context and complexity of the case by collecting data and facts through direct observation in the area.

The data collection technique in this study uses participatory observation. Participatory observation involves the researcher engaging in the daily activities of the people being observed or those used as sources of research data. Through this method, the data obtained will be more comprehensive, sharp, and capable of understanding the meaning behind every visible behavior. Additionally, data collection techniques include interviews, where questions and answers are conducted with individuals who can provide information directly. Other techniques include documentation study, literature study, and reviewing books and journals related to the problem being solved. The data analysis technique involves: 1) Data collection, 2) Data reduction and categorization, 3) Data display and conclusion drawing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Baranangsiang is a village located in the Cipongkor District of West Bandung Regency, covering an area of 15.53 square kilometers. The village consists of 59 neighborhood units (RT) and 11 community units (RW), with a total population of 9,129 residents.

Table 1: Population of Baranangsiang Village

No.	Information	Amount
1.	Total population	9.129
2.	Children aged 13-24 years	1.845
3.	Middle school/MTS education	404
4.	SMA/SMK education	87
5.	College Level	30

From Table 4.1, it shows the total population of Baranangsiang Village is 9,129 people, consisting of males and females who have received education ranging from Junior High School (SMP/MTS) to higher education levels, totaling 521 individuals 249 males and 272 females. Specifically, at the Junior High School (SMP)/Madrasah Tsanawiah (MTs) level, there are 404 individuals 194 males and 210 females. At the Vocational High School (SMK/SMA) level, there are 87 individuals 46 males and 41 females. Over the past three years, 30 individuals have continued to higher education, comprising 9 males and 21 females. At the Vocational High School (SMK/SMA) level, there are 87 individuals 46 males and 41 females. Over the past three years, 30 individuals have continued to higher education, comprising 9 males and 21 females. Additionally, 11 individuals were married at a young age. The research results indicate that gender equality in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, is nearly achieved, but there are some girls who aspire to pursue higher education yet face inadequate support from parents due to economic constraints. Moreover, parental perceptions that girls will ultimately end up in the kitchen make it challenging for them to pursue higher education.

1. Parents' Perception of Women's Rights in the Field of Education in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency

The term "perspective" or "perception" according to Yan Pramadya (1989:240) is the optimistic expectation for the future. Sobur (2013) defines perspective as a broad view, encompassing how someone perceives and interprets something. Suwarno describes perception as a process of drawing detailed and meaningful information from past experiences in specific situations (Siregar, 2013:12). According to Sahlan, parents constitute a family consisting of a father and mother, the result of a lawful marriage that forms a family unit. The parents' perception referred to in this study pertains to how parents view or consider their daughters' acquisition of education. As we know, parents have a responsibility to educate, nurture, and guide their children to how parents view or consider their daughters' acquisition of education. As we know, parents have a responsibility to educate, nurture, and guide their children to reach certain stages that prepare them for social life (Siregar, 2013:14).

Receiving a proper education is one of the fundamental rights of every human being, which must also be possessed by every woman. Human Rights (HAM) are a set of rights inherent to human existence as creatures of God, bestowed by Him and which must be respected for the honor, protection, and dignity of human beings. Without human rights, a person cannot be considered fully human, and if these rights are violated, the quality of their humanity diminishes as creations of God. According to Luhulima (2007:47), in the Republic of Indonesia

Law Number 7 of 1984 on the Convention on Women, it is explained that the United Nations Charter (PBB) strengthens the belief in human rights, dignity, and personal worth, as well as equal rights between men and women, it is explained that the United Nations Charter (PBB) strengthens the belief in human rights, dignity, and personal worth, as well as equal rights between men and women without distinction. Therefore, Human Rights are inherent rights within every human being, and without these rights, one cannot live as a human being.

The right to education is a fundamental human right for every individual, both men and women, as citizens. Every citizen has the right to receive education up to the highest level. Educational levels are stages of education determined by the developmental level of the learners, with several goals to be achieved and skills to be developed, as stated by Abdurrahman et al. (2022: 3). Education is a conscious and planned effort to achieve the learning process, enabling learners to actively develop their potential, acquire skills, and form good character. Rahmayani (2017) highlights the economic progress goals of education, emphasizing that education cannot be disregarded as it plays a crucial role, particularly in economic growth. Many women are marginalized for various reasons, including lower educational attainment compared to men.

Discussing education, as observed in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, especially in RT 06 RW 04, there is a high dropout rate among school-age children in this village. Many children prefer to work rather than continue their education, especially at the higher education level. Most residents of Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency view education as highly important. As stated by Mrs. Ade and others, education is crucial, especially nowadays, as it facilitates obtaining decent employment opportunities. This sentiment is echoed by Mrs. Salamah, emphasizing the importance of education; even as women, education cannot be ignored. Both formal and non-formal education are mandatory for both men and women, as long as it respects their nature as women.

To pursue education, a child definitely needs support from their family, especially parents. According to Krisnalita (2018: 76), education is the most important foundation for life. Through education, one can enhance their quality of life, including economic status, thinking skills, and behavior. Conversely, low educational quality is a major cause of human resource crises. Education is obtained through teaching and should be provided to everyone, regardless of gender, aiming for proper and quality education.

2. Women's Rights in Education

Human Rights are fundamental rights inherent to all individuals from birth. Human Rights can be understood as rights inherent to human nature. Without these rights, individuals would violate the rights of others, lacking mutual respect and appreciation for each other (Andhara et al., 2023: 1). This aligns with Krisnalita's statement (2018: 73) that Human Rights aim to ensure the dignity of every person and protect human dignity under applicable law, rights that cannot be revoked by anyone, ensuring freedom and a dignified life. This is explained in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which upholds principles of humanity and discusses the elevation of human dignity.

Based on research in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, the right to education between men and women is nearly equal. In Baranangsiang Village, both women and men have the same fundamental rights, as expressed by Mr. Enang, stating that education should not differentiate between genders. A man will become the head of the household, while a woman will become a mother who educates her children to have good morals. Furthermore, according to Mrs. Kristin, lacking education significantly impacts the ethical and polite behavior formation of a child.

Furthermore, the education held by women as citizens will impact their rights and political participation, as well as economic development within society. As observed in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, it shows that women's participation in politics is quite substantial. A woman, like a man, has the right to participate in political activities, both in policy-making and implementing those policies. This includes the right to vote, to be elected, and to participate in organizations related to the government in the country where she resides (Krisalita, 2018: 76).

From this explanation, it is clear that education can support women in participating in political fields as long as they do not violate the norms and agreements accepted by society. Therefore, in political life, women have the right to vote and to be elected. Women also have the right to equal opportunities with men to participate in formulating government policies. As written by Luhulima (2007: 73), in the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 7 of 1984, it is affirmed that women have the same rights as men: the right to be elected and to vote, the right to participate in formulating and implementing government policies, and the right to participate in organizations related to community and state politics.

This is consistent with what Savitri (2008: 3) expressed: that women are part of society with rights equal to those of men and are entitled to the guarantees and fundamental rights as stated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, although it does not explicitly state the guarantees of women's human rights. However, Article 2 of the Declaration reinforces that rights and freedoms are to be held by everyone, women and men alike, without discrimination.

Looking at the explanation above, it is clear that education plays a crucial role in empowering women to be more productive and actively participate in community, national, and state affairs, and cannot be simply overlooked. This is because intelligent children are born from mothers who are educated, nurtured, and raised within the family as the primary and fundamental means of education, thus expected to contribute to the development of a cultured, independent, and advanced nation. Education is something of utmost importance to possess, both for men and women.

3. The Impact of Parents' Perception on Girls' Rights in Education

Parents' views on girls often position them as marginalized or secondary individuals. The assumption that girls' roles will ultimately return to domestic duties diminishes their opportunities to pursue higher education. Consequently, in many rural areas of Indonesia, education for girls is often neglected. Such perceptions contribute to a lack of awareness among girls about pursuing higher education.

The lack of awareness to continue education to higher levels, especially among girls, is caused by several main factors as articulated by Natasha (2013: 56): (a) Stereotyping that attaches negative labels to girls such as weak, timid, and sensitive, which creates a contrast with boys who are labeled strong, brave, and resilient. (b) Subordination, where girls are consistently placed in lower positions across various fields. (c) Marginalization, leading to women being sidelined, particularly in economic and educational aspects, and not recognized as the backbone of the family, resulting in lower incomes and predominantly technical and routine jobs. (d) Double burden experienced by career women, who not only manage household chores but also carry the additional burden of their careers. (e) Violence, both physical and psychological, which Ahmad (2001: 31) identifies as a consequence of gender discrimination.

Based on research findings in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, many women have achieved gender equality in education, employment, decision-making, and political participation. However, several factors hinder women from pursuing higher education, particularly at the university level.

These include parental perceptions towards girls' education, economic factors, lack of interest from children in continuing education, and insufficient parental support. These factors contribute to the lower educational attainment among women in Baranangsiang Village, Cipongkor District, West Bandung Regency, particularly at the university level.

From the explanation above, there are both educated boys and girls ranging from Junior High School (SMP) to university level, totaling 521 individuals, comprising 249 boys and 272 girls. Specifically, there are 404 individuals at the Junior High School (SMP)/Madrasah Tsanawiah (MTs) level, 87 at the Vocational High School (SMK) level, and 30 who continued to university in the last three years.

Additionally, 11 individuals married at an early age. The research findings reveal that several girls intend to pursue higher education; however, inadequate parental support and economic circumstances make it challenging for them to achieve this goal.

4. The Importance of Education for Women from the Perspective of Civic Education

Education is the most fundamental basis, especially as preparation for the future. With education, a person can improve the quality of their life, such as economic quality, quality of thought, and behavior. Therefore, education must be provided to everyone, both men and women, to develop all the potential within them and positively impact the common good.

Education is also very important for women, as they are the pillars of a nation's existence. Women need to understand many things to support their roles as wives and mothers who will educate the nation's future generations. Krisnalita (2018: 76) states that women's obligation to seek knowledge is not limited to certain fields, but it has now expanded to encompass a wide range of disciplines, with the hope that educated women can shape future generations.

Education can encourage women as citizens to be competent and participate in various societal matters. Civic education views that every citizen has the right to receive education, as stated in the constitutional mandate of Article 31, paragraph 1, which says that every citizen has the right

to education and teaching. This implies that both men and women should have equal opportunities to receive education.

According to Winataputra (2015), civic education can be conceptually viewed from three dimensions: as a field of scientific study within educational science, as a curricular program in formal and non-formal educational institutions, and as enculturation in the context of national life. Therefore, civic education deeply examines various social issues currently developing in society. Stereotypes about gender issues and the marginalization of women in education and other fields are also subjects of study in civic education.

Azra, in Ubaedillah and Abdul Rozak (2013:15), explains that civic education is broader in scope than democracy education and human rights education because it includes the study and discussion of many things, such as government, constitution, democratic institutions, the rule of law, citizens' rights and duties, the democratic process, active participation, and citizens' involvement in civil society, knowledge about institutions and systems in government, politics, public administration, and legal systems, knowledge about human rights, active citizenship, and so on. Based on the definition provided by Azyumardi Azra, the role of civic education is not only to make citizens understand their rights and obligations but also to play an important role in providing knowledge about democracy and human rights to achieve equality for both men and women.

The female population comprises almost half of Indonesia's total population, representing a significant potential for achieving progress and a higher quality of life. Equality of conditions for men and women to obtain opportunities and rights as humans is necessary to enable them to participate and contribute in political, economic, legal, socio-cultural, educational, national defense, and security activities, as well as to enjoy the benefits of development. The 1945 Constitution, Chapter X on citizens, Article 27, paragraph (1) states, "Every citizen shall have an equal position before the law and government and shall uphold the law and the government without exception.

without exception. This result further underscores the importance of women's empowerment, particularly in supporting aspects of women's empowerment that will significantly contribute to development, especially in increasing the rate of economic growth. The goals of equality in education include ending discrimination against women, eliminating various forms of violence against women, and reducing the rate of early marriage.

According to Gultom (2012: 95), many forms of violence often occur in society, such as sexual violence and the rape of young girls, where most incidents involve someone they know, such as a relative or friend. Putri (2022) states that gender inequality in education can lead to injustice between men and women, especially in education. This is caused by several factors, one of which is economic.

From an economic perspective, men and women have the same responsibilities. Gender refers to the differences between men and women in roles, functions, and behaviors shaped by socio-cultural values or customs (Puspitawati: 2013).

According to Soemantri (1992: 92), generally, every constitution contains three main components, one of which is the regulation on the protection of human rights and citizens. Therefore, all legislation related to citizenship, particularly women's citizenship rights, must be based on the Constitution as the fundamental norm.

It should explicitly state Pancasila as the ideological foundation and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia as the constitutional foundation. Substantively, it must reflect the principles contained in Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution.

This aligns with the views of Elin, a resident of RT 06 RW 04, who said that when a woman lacks education or her right to education is restricted, she will not have broad experience and knowledge. This is consistent with what Mrs. Reni stated, that when someone is uneducated, they will lack the foundation for the future and will not have the skills to secure a decent job.

From the explanation above, the author concludes that education for women cannot be disregarded, especially today. When a girl is not equipped with sufficient knowledge or skills, job opportunities for women become more limited. Furthermore, in society, many instances of exclusion and violence against women in employment, households, and other areas are due to low educational levels.

Therefore, from the perspective of civic education, education should be accessible to both boys and girls because it is a right for every citizen. Additionally, the country needs maximum support from women to achieve sustainable national development. Women in the 4.0 era play a significant role as strong and resilient individuals, wives, mothers, and citizens responsible for contributing to the welfare of Indonesian society and the nation's progress.

CONCLUSION

From the explanation above, the author can draw the following conclusions:

1. Parents' perceptions of girls' educational rights in Barangsiang Village, Cipongkor Subdistrict, West Bandung Regency significantly influence the education levels in the area, particularly for girls. This village has a notable dropout rate. Most young people in this village prefer to work rather than continue their education, especially at the higher education level. For girls, many choose to marry or work due to a lack of parental support and persistent stigmas such as the belief that girls do not need higher education because they will ultimately end up in the kitchen, taking care of children, and other views that hinder their motivation to pursue higher education.
2. In Barangsiang Village, girls are now given the right to education and have the same opportunities as boys, although this is not yet fully realized. Girls are granted the freedom to attain higher education, but this opportunity is not seized by every girl due to various limitations, including economic factors, lack of parental support, and other constraints.

3. Parents' perceptions of girls' educational rights significantly hinder girls from continuing their education, especially at the higher education level, due to insufficient parental support. Consequently, the level of higher education attainment among girls in Barangsiang Village, Cipongkor Subdistrict, West Bandung Regency is relatively low.
4. From the perspective of civic education, both boys and girls should have access to education as it is a right for every citizen. Women play significant roles as individuals, wives, mothers, and citizens, all of whom have equal rights and obligations to contribute positively to the nation's progress in the current 4.0 era. This support is crucial for enhancing the welfare of Indonesian society and advancing the nation.

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